

SMART PARTNERSHIP: RING & ROLL, TWIST LONG JOHN

^aSiti Nazmin Binti Mohd Yatim

^bFarahida Binti Sazali

^cRohana Binti Ramli

^{abc}SMK Syed Mashor, Selangor, Malaysia

^a*ppki.smksm.5065@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to explore, understand and explain the implementation of the Smart Partnership Project: Ring & Roll, Twist Long John for the students with Special Needs Learning Disabilities (MBK BP) at SMK Syed Mashor, Hulu Selangor. A total of 8 students with moderate functional learning difficulties, 2 teachers and a PPM were involved in this study. Preliminary surveys found that the students, teachers and PPM faced some problems in following the bread making skills based on the National Occupational Skill Standard (NOSS) provided by the Department of Skills Development (JPK). Smart Partnership Project: Ring & Roll, Twist Long John is implemented to create a smart partnership between the school and professionals in related industries. Qualitative methods and case study strategies were conducted for data collection and analysis through the observation, interview and document analysis methods. The findings of the study have been able to identify and explain in detail about the implementation of the Smart Partnership Project: Ring & Roll, Twist Long John MBK BP in this school. As a result, the study was successfully and the module will be designed so that it can be used as a guideline as an implementation of smart partnership in the future.

Keywords: Bread making, moderate functional learning difficulties, NOSS, Smart Partnership, Ring, Roll, Twist, Long John, Malaysian Skills Certificate.

1. Introduction

The role and responsibility of a Special Education teacher is not only to teach theory in the classroom to students with special needs (MBK), but also to educate and train this MBK in practice so that the knowledge and skills that need to be mastered, can be utilized and used this MBK properly. when they enter the world of work after finishing school. Parents have high expectations of teachers and schools in order for their children's learning outcomes at school to help MBK children get a job that allows them to be independent, support themselves, and continue to survive without relying entirely on family members, especially if both parents have died. The role of the Ministry of Education Malaysia (MOE) is to provide clear educational policies in assisting special education teachers and MBK so that the direction of special education can be understood by all stakeholders and achieved successfully. MOE provides a holistic curriculum and in accordance with the needs of MBK so that the survival of MBK can continue well after school.

The Special Education Division (BPKhas) has outlined several missions in developing excellent human capital with special needs. It is providing a quality, relevant and holistic

education system, development of one's potential to the optimum level, competitiveness and marketability, noble values as a responsible citizen, smart partnerships with various parties and the internationalization of Special Education Programmes. In achieving the missions outlined, KPM has provided various initiatives to ensure that MBKs who graduate from school, are able to have aspects of marketability in the field of employment, especially MBKs who have academic problems such as not being able to follow the mainstream curriculum, do not fully master the basics of reading, writing and arithmetic (3M), having problems communicating (introvert or extrovert) with people around them as well as self-management and behavior problems. Therefore, this MBK should be given the opportunity to learn and master vocational skills as an alternative to the existing academic knowledge. Therefore, various initiatives, programmes and skills institutions have been introduced or created by the MOE. It is formulating a comprehensive Special Education Curriculum, holding a Special Vocational Education Secondary School (SMPKV), creating a Buying Seat programme, drafting a Standard Secondary School Curriculum (KSSM), as well as the Upper Secondary Industrial Apprenticeship Programme (PIMA). These programmes are among the alternatives to the academic streams that are usually difficult to master by most MBKs who are usually more inclined towards skill areas.

Starting in 2016, simultaneously with the implementation of KSSM PK and the introduction of KVS subjects, MOE also in collaboration with JPK and the Center for Instructor Training and Advanced Skill Training (CIAST) has seriously held a pilot school project, organizing a series of workshops and courses in person and online specifically to train potential special education teachers as head coaches (JUs) who in turn will guide other special education teachers who teach KVS subjects, so that they have at least a Level 3 SKM certificate and provide opportunities to as well as encourage teachers to continue to have Vocational Training Officer (VTO) certificate qualification.

MOE also encourages schools to take the initiative to create an Accredited Center (PB) for National Occupational Skill Standard (NOSS) which has been selected to be implemented in the school and in accordance with the ability of students and NOSS requirements outlined by the Department of Skills Development (JPK) for certification accreditation. SKM for MBK can be implemented in the PB. School administrators, especially principals, are encouraged to obtain Induction Certificates provided by JPK to be eligible to be appointed as PB Managers in their respective schools so that there is continuity in the implementation of KVS in schools, starting from the Principal, administrators, school staff and then the MBK.

Recognizing the operating costs and financial implications related to the implementation of KVS subjects for the purpose of learning and accreditation of SKM for MBK is too expensive to be borne by the school if it only relies on existing per capita grant assistance (PCG), through Financial Circular Letter (SPK) Number 1 Year 2021 which was improved to SPK Number 8 Year 2012 and Amendments to SPK Number 8 Year 2012, KPM has taken the initiative to provide PCG assistance specifically for KVS subjects with SKM qualification, at a rate of RM800 to RM1600 per student per year. The PCG rate per student per year varies according to the NOSS list. For the subject of basic vocational skills (KAV), which is a subject that provides basic vocational skills for MBK who follow KSSM PK Form 1, PCG provided is at the rate of RM150 per student per year.

According to Kohler and Field (2003) in Rosmiza MZ, Mimi Halida Ghazali (2019), the determinants of the success of the Career Transition Programme (PTK) or pre-vocational training to MBK BP are student-centered planning, student development, inter-agency and multidisciplinary collaboration, family involvement as well as programme structure. According to Noonan et al. (2008), the best strategies for conducting effective collaboration start at the federal, state, district and school levels.

Special Education teachers need to be creative and innovative in implementing the curriculum provided in accordance with the potential and abilities of MBK. The Education (Special Education) Regulations 2013, under item 8 paragraph (1) (c) states, a teacher may modify the methods or techniques of teaching and learning, the time allocated for each activity, arrangement of activities and teaching aids. While item 8 paragraph (2) states that any modification in paragraph (1) (c) shall be in accordance with the Special Education Curriculum.

In this regard, to overcome the various challenges in teaching KVS subjects in schools in an effort to prepare MBK for SKM accreditation, the Smart Partnership programme was implemented in the Special Education Integration Programme of SMK Syed Mashor (PPKI SMKSM) involving 8 students, 2 teachers and 2 Assistants Pupil Management (PPM) with 2 lecturers from Hulu Selangor Community College. The content of the programme is to conduct 2 series of courses for the Doughnut Making Competency Unit (CU), namely the skills of producing four types of doughnuts. This Smart Partnership Programme has the full support of parents who hope that aspects of their children's life skills can be further improved with the help of professionals in related industries.

Since the students started of taking this KVS subject in 2019, it has been found that students still have difficulty mastering the required skills. The Smart Partnership Programme with Hulu Selangor Community College proposed in this study is a programme designed with a specific purpose to overcome the challenges in the teaching and learning of KVS subjects. The programme is implemented to enhance the knowledge and skills of teachers and students to produce the four types of doughnuts outlined in the Doughnut Preparation CU.

The main objective of this study is to explore, understand and explain the implementation of the Smart Partnership Project: Ring & Roll, Twist Long John MBK Learning Problems PPKI SMK Syed Mashor. In particular, the specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Improve the skills of making four types of doughnuts.
2. Complete the physical requirements and equipment to achieve the Malaysian Skills Certificate (SKM) standard.
3. Improve the teachers' skills and get recognition from JPK.
4. Prepare the project modules as guidelines to implement the PPKI smart partnership programme.

The Smart Partnership Programme: Ring & Roll, Twist Long John has had a positive impact on MBK and teachers. The results of the interviews after the programme was implemented, found that the MBK involved felt very happy because they had mastered the skills of making four types of doughnuts, namely ring, roll, twist and long john, better than before. Teachers also feel more confident in teaching the CU and this saves time because students have also shown increased understanding, skills and self-confidence to complete assignments without waiting for the teacher's instructions at all times.

2. Methodology

This study was conducted using a qualitative method approach. The case study strategies were conducted to collect and analyze data through observation, interview and document analysis methods. For this study, the researcher used the PDCA cycle of Plan, Do, Check and Action to achieve the objectives (Figure 1).

Figure 1: PDCA cycle

Source: (The W.Edwards Deming Institute, 2015)

2.1 Step 1: Plan

Data collection was done using document analysis on work forms that recorded the student 's performance after completing assignments. There are four main components of evaluation that are present in the work form, namely attitude, job safety, work process and work results. As a result of the analysis of this document, several problems have been identified. Among them are students who lack the determination to complete the task in the allotted time, students who are unable to produce doughnuts in the allotted time, and students who are unable to produce doughnuts in accordance with the five doughnut criteria required, which are shape, texture, aroma, colour, and taste.

Based on the data collected, the researchers found that the main problem of students with learning difficulties not mastering the basic skills of doughnut is because they are too dependent on the teacher to complete assignments. The basic skills of reading, writing and counting are also not well mastered by them. As a result, the doughnut production process is disrupted. Teachers take a long time to teach the basics of doughnut production due to the background of students who consist of various learning problems such as autism and Attention-deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD).

Teachers had to repeat teaching instructions and demonstrations several times to help students to really master the skills taught, while students took a long time to understand the process and work steps written on the whiteboard or notepaper given to them. Pupils will also need several reinforcement exercises in recognizing the texture and shape of the ingredients, reading the names of the ingredients and measuring the ingredients correctly according to the proportions required in the doughnut recipe. Pupils also have difficulty understanding, remembering and using the correct hardware to complete an assignment. Pupils take a long time to get to know the hardware. At times, the teachers also have trouble choosing the appropriate approach to teach these students to produce four types of doughnuts well.

2.2 Step 2: Do

For the purpose of overcoming the problems faced, the smart partnership project was planned and implemented on 5 March 2020 and 11 March 2020 after discussing with the teaching staff

of Hulu Selangor Community College with the permission of the Director of Hulu Selangor Community College and the Principal of SMK Syed Mashor. The smart partnership of doughnut production is implemented in phases, namely Phase 1 and Phase 2. The expertise of the teaching staff in the same industry is very necessary for teachers to use as a reference and add new knowledge. Pupils are also given the opportunity to learn directly from the instructors related to the technique of producing four types of doughnuts correctly. The implementation of two series also gives more space for students to practice the skills of producing the four types of doughnuts learned. The sharing of knowledge with the professional teaching staff also provides an opportunity for teachers to gain knowledge and techniques to teach students better to master the skills outlined in the relevant CU. Figure 2 shows a smart partnership session conducted at Hulu Selangor Community College.

Figure 2: The picture shows the initial information session and the activity of measuring materials correctly with the teaching staff of Hulu Selangor Community College.

2.3 Step 3: Check

Figure 3 shows the work process of students undergoing a session. Pupils are given a probationary period within the first hour. Then the student's work is isolated. Next, the students are given a period of two hours to reproduce doughnuts from the first step for the purpose of strengthening and psychomotor training of students in order to master the necessary skills.

Figure 3: The picture shows the process of producing four types of doughnuts.

2.4 Step 4: Action

Figure 4 shows the final step in the PDCA. The researcher used the work form to evaluate the four components in the student work form through the activities carried out. Pupils are more confident in producing doughnuts and are able to complete assignments at the given time without relying entirely on the teacher. Pupils and teachers are also given certificates by the Hulu Selangor Community College and this is an added value to each student's portfolio in the SKM accreditation effort.

Figure 4: The picture shows the process of the final doughnut and the certificate obtained from Hulu Selangor Community College.

3. Results

The study was conducted for four months from January to March 2020 and August to October 2020. Prior to the Smart Partnership Programme, students found it extremely difficult to master the skills of making doughnuts. Repetition of instructions and demonstrations is done repeatedly by the teacher for the students to master one by one the required skills. As a result, students take longer than necessary to complete the Doughnut Making CU.

Table 1 shows the results of document analysis from the working form before the Smart Partnership Programme was conducted. All 8 students were found to be very weak at preparing doughnuts in the allotted time and very weak in determining the doughnut production steps.

Table 1: The table shows the level of mastery of students' skills based on the work forms recorded before the programme was conducted.

COMPONENT	ACHIEVEMENT LEVEL	PUPIL							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
ATTITUDE	1. Creative, cleanliness and work practices.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Practice good work.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	3. Practice good food hygiene.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	4. Duration of task completing.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
WORK SAFETY	1. Compliance with safety regulations.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Apply safety skills.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	3. Used kitchen rules.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	4. All equipment is close after used.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
WORK PROCESS	1. Determine the right tools.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Materials selection.	/	/	/	/	X	X	/	/
	3. Determine the steps of making doughnut.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	4. Mise en place run.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	5. Duration of work process.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
WORK RESULT	1. Choose the tools and utensils.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Materials selection.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	3. Doughnut production according to the recipe.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	4. Doughnut criteria (shape, texture, aroma, colour, taste)	/	/	/	X	X	X	X	X

Instructions: (/) Accept (X) Do not accept

After the Smart Partnership Programme was carried out, the teaching and learning process can be implemented more smoothly. Pupils can master the techniques and skills of

producing four types of doughnuts without having to rely entirely on the teacher. Pupils are also able to produce doughnuts within a set period of time. Pupils can measure materials correctly and are proficient in using hardware that is properly functional.

As a result of teacher observation and analysis of work forms, students showed improved mastery of skills. Records on student work forms record student achievement better than before. 5 out of 8 students were found to have successfully produced doughnuts in the allotted time and all 8 students were able to determine the doughnut production steps.

However, it was found that 3 out of 8 students still need to master the skills of preparing doughnuts in the allotted time. There are two major factors that have been identified as the cause of these skills not being mastered: it was discovered that 2 out of every 8 students frequently do not attend school and that 1 out of every 8 students has intellectual problems from birth, which is difficulty processing information in a fast time.

Table 2: The table shows the level of mastery of students' skills based on the work forms recorded after the programme was conducted.

COMPONENT	ACHIEVEMENT LEVEL	PUPIL							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
ATTITUDE	1. Creative, cleanliness and work practices.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Practice good work.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	3. Practice good food hygiene.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	4. Duration of task completing.	/	/	/	X	X	X	/	/
WORK SAFETY	1. Compliance with safety regulations.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Apply safety skills.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	3. Used kitchen rules.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	4. All equipment is close after used.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
WORK PROCESS	1. Determine the right tools.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Materials selection.	/	/	/	/	X	X	/	/
	3. Determine the steps of making doughnut.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	4. Mise en place run.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	5. Duration of work process.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
WORK RESULT	1. Choose the tools and utensils.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	2. Materials selection.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	3. Doughnut production according to the recipe.	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	4. Doughnut criteria (shape, texture, aroma, colour, taste)	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/

Instructions: (/) Accept (X) Do not accept

Findings of information from students through interviews are arranged according to themes so that the information obtained is easy to handle and can be used as a conclusion for this study. Question 1 in Table 3 was asked of the students in order for the researcher to

learn about the students' prior experience and knowledge of doughnut production before they began learning CU Doughnut Production.

Table 3: The table shows the students' response to Question 1 submitted by the teacher.

Question 1: Before the programme with Hulu Selangor Community College, did you ever make doughnuts at home?	
PUPIL	RESPONSE
1	<i>"I helped my mom..I just looked at it..."</i>
2	<i>"I seldom helped my mom, because my mom sells cake"</i>
3	<i>"Never.."</i>
4	<i>"Never..only my mom did it..I didn't."</i>
5	<i>"No..only my mom did it. I just ate."</i>
6	<i>"Never..I don't know how to make it."</i>
7	<i>"I helped my mom..It was so delicious."</i>
8	<i>"I helped my mom but not everyday."</i>

The results of this question found that 7 out of 8 students did not have direct experience at home in doughnut production. This shows that students do not have solid existing knowledge to be applied in doughnut making training in school. This causes teachers to present the theory and practice of doughnut production repeatedly so that each student understands the steps of material selection and preparation of doughnuts in the allotted time. There are times when the teacher has to repeat the same instruction more than 8 times for 8 students with different levels of understanding so that each student understands and can remember well the steps of preparing doughnuts. This is definitely taking more time than targeted. KVS teaching time is 28 times a week. Sometimes teachers have to teach for more than a week on the topic of doughnut making due to students having difficulty understanding the analysis of assignments required.

Question 2 in Table 4 was asked by the students for the purpose of the researcher collecting information about the students' experience of completing the doughnut making task with the teacher in the school. Researchers want to identify what problems of the students faced during the learning process of the topic.

Table 4: The table shows the students' response to Question 2 submitted by the teacher.

Question 2: While at school, is it easy to make doughnuts with the teacher?	
PUPIL	RESPONSE
1	<i>"It was great. I can do it. Lack of time in the beginning."</i>
2	<i>"I need to ask teacher yet it will be difficult."</i>
3	<i>"Yes I can do it but it is difficult."</i>
4	<i>"Yes I can do it."</i>
5	<i>"Yes I can do it.It is difficult.I could not memorize the ingredients."</i>
6	<i>"It is hard even the teacher had helped me. I could not finish to make the doughnut."</i>
7	<i>"It is hard in the beginning but I managed to do it."</i>
8	<i>"It is ok, but it is better if teacher could help."</i>

The findings from the answer to question 2 showed that, although the students were assisted by the teacher in preparing doughnuts at school, all 8 students still had difficulty mastering the skills learned. Pupils still find it difficult to complete assignments and rely on the

teacher if they experiencing related problems. Pupils have the difficulty remembering the process, work steps and materials, are still not confident in being independent and need teacher guidance for solving problems encountered throughout the doughnut preparation process.

The researcher then asked the students of Question 3 to find out what their personal feelings and opinions were when given the opportunity to participate in this Smart Partnership programme in two phases. The purpose of the questions asked was also to examine the effectiveness of the programme and aspects of improvement from the point of view of students.

Table 5: The table shows the students' response to Question 3 submitted by the teacher.

Question 3: What are your feelings and opinions while undergoing a programme with Community College?	
PUPIL	RESPONSE
1	<i>"There are a lot of big tables and the teachers are very understanding."</i>
2	<i>"I felt very happy. I could learn how to make many types of doughnuts."</i>
3	<i>"I felt very happy. There is a big kitchen and there are a lot of utensils."</i>
4	<i>"I like it because teachers explain it clearly."</i>
5	<i>"I felt very happy because I could learn how to make many types of doughnuts. The sink and the kitchen is big, there is a big table. Very comfortable."</i>
6	<i>"I like it because the kitchen is very big. We could make doughnuts very comfortable with our friends."</i>
7	<i>"We could bring the doughnuts to our house. It supplied a box too."</i>
8	<i>"I like it. We did not share the utensils with friends. Our moms could eat the doughnuts too. They said the doughnuts is very delicious too."</i>

Findings from Question 3 showed that the students were happy with the Smart Partnership programme conducted. Pupils were comfortable with the method of teaching by the teaching staff from the Community College. The teaching method of the instructors helped them to understand easily, produce doughnuts in the allotted time and also showed that the aspect of comfortable facilities at Hulu Selangor Community College also got the attention of the students.

4. Discussion

The preparation of MBK in the basic aspects of vocational skills provides support to MBK to follow the teaching and learning process at PPKI better, orderly and systematically before they follow the Malaysian Skills Certificate course to prepare for a career. According to the People with Disabilities Act (2008), MBK's involvement in vocational training is lifelong and they should be given educational opportunities and space just like mainstream students. As a special education teacher, researchers are always ready to improve teaching methods in order to be adapted to the MBK of various abilities in a single special education class. The selection of the right teaching techniques and methods will help speed up the comprehension process by MBKs so that they are able to master the skills needed to complete the assignment in a well-set time.

Based on the study conducted, the researchers found that there are positive stimuli as a result of the implementation of this Smart Partnership programme that contributes to the mastery of skills and psychological aspects of the students. Students successfully complete assignments if several important factors, such as doughnut preparation information

presentation method by the teacher is easy to understand, adequate equipment for all the students, comfortable workshop size for students to move and having a work table suitable for students to place materials and equipment.

In the aspect of SKM accreditation, it is very important for the students to master each skill well so that the practical test session in the final year of their studies at school for accreditation can be conducted smoothly. JPK has prepared modules arranged according to the requirements of NOSS Bread Making. This arrangement is based on the student's ability to provide a product. In addition, the module is divided into three parts, namely simple, medium and difficult recipes and need to be processed according to the student's ability. Consideration should also be made when it comes to teaching and learning that involves the production of products that take a long time and are unavoidable.

The recipe was given to the students must be detailed because this MBK will follow what is in the recipe carefully. For example, most of the MBK is weak in terms of 3M mastery, namely reading, writing and counting. Therefore, the recipe given should be more of a visual recipe, and including the steps of preparing a product is also visual. Through pictorial steps, MBK is easier to understand and practice in the classroom.

In addition, the module should be equipped with a method of arrangement and storage of information that is used in a more orderly structure to facilitate the process of accreditation of SKM Bread Making to competent students. All information and recipes given will be collected and documented to facilitate students to practice preparing the products learned.

For the purpose of improving the existing practical workshops in the school, this Smart Partnership Programme has provided effective input in helping teachers to select and purchase industry-standard equipment and hardware that meet the specifications set out in NOSS Bread Making. Furthermore, the teaching and learning process can also be strengthened through continuous practical training by using adequate hardware and equipment. The teacher acts as a facilitator who is always ready to guide each student according to their diverse abilities.

Throughout this study, the researchers have identified several factors that contribute to the effectiveness of the implementation of KVS to students, namely:

- a) practical workshops must be equipped with facilities appropriate to the relevant industry, always conducive and appropriate to the number of students;
- b) the equipment needed for practicals must be sufficient so that students are not left behind in any learning content.

While the aspects that need to be improved by teachers are:

- a) the competence of teachers as teachers in schools should be given priority;
- b) The use of soft skills should be used.
- c) teachers need to have credentials and recognition from the JPK in order to master the content of the subject well and be able to choose the best techniques to help students to be proficient in each CU under NOSS Bread Making.

Researchers will implement improvements to ensure that the programme is carried out to meet the set standards and can be used as a benchmark for other schools.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The smart partnership project carried out is very suitable to be carried out by involving MBK in the learning of Vocational Skills to determine the direction of their careers according to their respective areas of ability. Their learning experiences are based on an experience-based theory by David Kolb (1984) that emphasizes learning through individual experience. involves the application of theory to actual practice for the process of understanding learning in a more effective direction. Through this theory of experience, learning runs in stages according to rounds to ensure that it achieves the set objectives.

Overall, this project can be implemented successfully and have a positive impact on the implementation of the KVS curriculum in schools. The factors that influence the effectiveness of this project are careful programme planning, the readiness of teachers and students to master vocational skills and the involvement of parents, schools and Hulu Selangor Community College who always provide support to ensure MBK in their field. Smart partnerships can also be continued by involving more professionals and agencies that can enhance the potential of MBK.

The experience gained during the implementation of the study has given the idea to the researcher to produce the Smart Partnership Module Ring & Roll, Twist Long John, which can be used as a guideline for the implementation of the KVS training programme for teachers involved with PdPc MBK.

The implementation of this Smart Partnership Programme is also expected to help all parties run the programme to produce MBK that is competitive and has a high marketability value. The success of implementing the Smart Partnership programme with industry experts will have a significant impact on Students with Special Needs (MBK) to better face their future not only in the field of bakery but also in the various fields in which they are involved.

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